

virescens (see table). The early-planted crops were significantly more severely infected with RTV, resulting in lower grain yield, than late planting. Severe RTV infection in the early samba crop was due to overlapping of younger plants with the sornavari season (May planting) older crop that had high RTV incidence and vector population. When the vector population declined later, RTV incidence also was reduced. We concluded that the spread of RTV was mainly influenced by the vector population. □

Effect of planting time and field population of green leafhopper on RTV incidence.^a Tirur, India, 1984.

Planting date	RTV incidence ^b (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	GLH in light trap (no./mo)
10 Aug	68.6 g	0.97 e	Jul : 181,196
20 Aug	60.6 f	1.77 d	Aug : 30,343
30 Aug	19.6 e	2.60 c	Sep : 2,407
10 Sep	8.1 d	2.43 c	Oct : 906
20 Sep	1.9 c	4.27 a	Nov : 1,278
30 Sep	2.1 c	3.60 b	
10 Oct	1.0 b	2.57 c	
20 Oct	1.2 bc	2.57 c	
30 Oct	0.2 a	2.47 c	
CD (P = 0.05)	1.95	0.36	

^a Means in a column followed by a common letter are not statistically significant at the 5% level.

^b Mean of 3 replications.

A new annelidan pest of rice in Nepal

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A new pest of rice, tentatively named "Sano Gadeula" (small earthworm), was recorded in farmers' fields during the 1980 crop in the plains and hills of Nepal (see figure). The pest was identified in Japan as *Limnodrilus* sp., phylum Annelida and class Oligochaeta.

Fields infested with this pest

resemble Zn-deficient plots. Leaves of infested plants turn yellow or brown and the plant is stunted. Severely infested plants die.

Closer observation revealed newly hatched worms in the basal part of the plant tissue. Mature worms usually were found in clusters in the roots and the underground basal parts of the plant.

Feeding habits of the worm and plant injury are under study. The worm can survive in fresh water for several days, even without soil, but when exposed without water or soil,

Limnodrilus sp., a new pest of rice found in Nepal.

dies within a minute because of dehydration. □

Caseworm (CW) preference for vegetative stage rice

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CW *Nymphula depunctalis* moths oviposit on the undersides of leaves floating in water. In a no-choice test, most eggs were laid on floating leaves, a few on erect leaves, and some on leaves bent in water (Table 1).

In 13 plots exhibiting all plant growth stages, we randomly sampled 20 hills per growth stage and recorded the number of leaves touching the water. Only vegetative stage rice had significant numbers of leaves in contact with water.

A free-choice test measured

oviposition by seedling age. Potted plants of different ages were immersed in a drum filled with water set so that leaves of each age were at the same distance above the water surface. The number of eggs laid on seedlings 1, 2,

3, 4, and 5 wk after sowing did not differ.

A preference to oviposit on leaves 2, 4, 6, and 8 mm wide was tested.

Excised 4-wk-old floating leaves were randomly pinned to submerged stakes

Table 1. Ovipositional preference of *N. depunctalis* on IR36 rice at different plant ages.^a IIRI greenhouse, 1983-84.

Plant age ^b (WT)	Oviposition site ^c (no. eggs/10 females per 3 d)		
	Excised floating leaves	Leaves bent in water	Erect leaves
2	123 b	157 a	85 a
4	378 a	189 a	157 a
6	278 ab	153 a	37 b
8	201 ab	179 a	35 b
10	109 b	90 a	31 b
Mean	218	153	69

^a Av of 6 replications, 10 females and males per replication. Potted plants and excised leaves were placed in mesh-covered 44-gallon gasoline drum cages 3/4 full of water. Floating and bent leaves were pinned to submerged stakes. ^b Transplanted 3 wk after germination. WT = wk after transplanting.

^c In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.